

Physicochemical Studies in Mixed Solvents. Density and Viscosity Studies of Alkali and Alkaline Earth Metal Formates in Formic Acid + Acetonitrile Mixtures

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Viscosity and density of formates of lithium, sodium, potassium, calcium and barium in formic acid (FA)+acetonitrile (AN) mixtures containing 100, 80 and 20% (w/w) FA were measured at 303.15 K. The experimental results of viscosity have been analysed using the Jones-Dole equation. The activation parameters of viscous flow have been obtained to throw light on the mechanism of viscous flow. The apparent molar volumes of these electrolytes at different concentrations have been estimated which indicate that these behave as structure promoters.

VISCOSITY B -coefficients or apparent molar volumes like other transport properties of electrolyte solutions provide useful information about the kinetic entities of the salt solutions from which ion-solvent interactions can be inferred. Even though studies on ion-solvent interactions in mixed solvents¹⁻⁵ are quite extensive, literature provides less information of such studies in binary solvent systems, containing ionising cosolvent in general and where the anion of the ionising cosolvent is the same as the anion of the salt in particular. In continuation of our conductance studies⁶ of 1 : 1 electrolytes in formic acid + acetonitrile, density and viscosity measurements have been undertaken to obtain additional information about ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions in these systems.

Experimental

Formic acid (Riedel ; 98 – 100%) and acetonitrile (E. Merck) were purified⁷. Alkali and alkaline earth metal formates were prepared and purified as reported earlier⁸. Formic acid + acetonitrile mixtures and the solutions of electrolytes in these solvent mixtures were made by weight. Densities were measured with double capillary pycnometer as described earlier⁹. The precision in density determinations was within ± 2 parts in 10^4 which introduces an uncertainty of 0.1 to 1.0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ in ϕ_V values. Viscosity measurements were made with an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer with a flow time of 302 s for water at 303.15 K. The time of efflux through the capillary was measured correct upto ± 0.1 s. The viscometer was held in a water thermostat (± 0.02 K). Kinetic energy corrections were not applied since the flow times are sufficiently large.

The dielectric constants of the solvent mixtures at 303.15 K were measured with DK meter 60 GK

(Franzkustner Naef. K.G. Dresden) and the values are 50.65 for 80% formic acid + 20% acetonitrile, and 38.75 for 20% formic acid + 80% acetonitrile mixtures.

Results and Discussion

Viscosity (η) and density (d) of the salt solutions in FA + AN mixtures containing 100, 80 and 20% FA at 303.15 K and at different concentrations (C) are measured. The apparent molar volume (ϕ_V) was calculated from density data using equation (1),

$$\phi_V = \frac{M_2}{d_0} - \frac{1000(d - d_0)}{C d_0} \quad (1)$$

where, C is the molar concentration of the electrolyte, d the density of the solution, d_0 the density of the appropriate solvent mixture and M_2 the molecular weight of the electrolyte.

The relative viscosities (η_r) of electrolytes in FA + AN mixtures containing 100, 80 and 20% FA were determined. The viscosity data were analysed by Jones-Dole equation (2),

$$\eta_r = \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC \quad (2)$$

where, η_r is the relative viscosity of electrolytic solutions, A the Falkenhagen¹⁰ coefficient that takes into account ionic interactions and B the Jones-Dole coefficient related to the size of the ions and to the different ion-solvent interactions. A and B values were calculated by the method of least-squares by fitting the experimental results in the Jones-Dole equation (Table 1).

The values of A obtained for all salts (except barium salt) in 80% FA + 20% AN mixture and for potassium and calcium salts in 100% FA are negative. However, no significance could be attributed to this observation since such negative values are no

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TABLE 1—VALUES OF DIFFERENT PARAMETERS FOR ALKALI AND ALKALINE EARTH METAL FORMATES IN FORMIC ACID+ACETONITRILE MIXTURES AT 303.15 K

Formic acid in solvent mixture W %	A^a $\text{dm}^{3/2} \text{mol}^{-1/2}$	B^a $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ kJ mol^{-1}	ϕ_v^0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	S_v^0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1/2}$
Lithium formate					
100	0.026	0.52	19.67	23.06	5.41
80	-0.007	0.49	16.81	22.68	11.17
20	0.087	0.32	9.27	11.52	22.50
Sodium formate					
100	0.024	0.63	21.06	20.02	8.85
80	-0.041	0.63	18.38	18.31	14.16
20	0.008	0.38	9.92	8.17	23.71
Potassium formate					
100	-0.002	0.80	28.95	25.25	13.33
80	-0.003	0.75	20.14	24.52	15.08
20	0.112	0.45	11.04	14.36	25.55
Calcium formate					
100	-0.005	1.37	34.60	25.60	30.26
80	-0.042	1.34	28.61	24.00	68.75
Barium formate					
100	0.042	1.50	35.02	28.08	42.76
80	0.037	1.48	30.00	26.00	45.00

^aStandard deviation in A -coefficient values = $\pm 0.002-0.005$ and in B -coefficient values = $\pm 0.02-0.05$. ^bValues of $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ are 11.52, 9.62 and 5.37 for mixtures containing 100, 80 and 20% formic acid.

expected on the basis of Falkenhagen theory¹⁰. But many such cases are reported in the literature¹¹⁻¹³ in mixed solvents. The positive and large B values indicate that these salts function as structure-makers in the solvent mixtures. The structure-making tendency of the salts follows the order, Ba-salt > Ca-salt > K-salt > Na-salt > Li-salt. Further, B values increased with increase in formic acid concentration and this suggests that formic acid behaves as structure-maker.

The viscosity data is analysed on the basis of the transition state treatment of relative viscosity of the electrolytic solutions as suggested by Feakins *et al.*¹. The free energy of activation per mole of the pure solvent ($\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$) and the free energy of activation per mole of solute ($\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$) are calculated with the help of equations¹⁴ (3) and (4),

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0*} = RT \ln (\eta_0 \bar{V}_1^0 / hN) \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0*} = \Delta\mu_1^{0*} + \frac{RT}{\bar{V}_1^0} [1000 B - (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)] \quad (4)$$

where, h is the Planck constant, N the Avogadro number, η_0 and \bar{V}_1^0 are the viscosity and partial molar volume of the solvent and \bar{V}_2^0 is the partial molar volume of the solute. It is evident from the data (Table 1) that $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ is practically constant for all salts at each composition. This implies that B -coefficient is dependent mainly on $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ and $(\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)$ terms; μ_2^{0*} values are positive and larger than $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$. This suggests that the formation of the transition state is less favoured in presence of the salts, meaning that formation of the transition state

is accompanied by the breaking and distortion of the intermolecular bonds.

The apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) calculated from the density data varied linearly with the square-root of the concentration in conformity with the Masson equation¹⁵ (5),

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v^0 \sqrt{C} \quad (5)$$

The values of apparent molar volume at infinite dilution ($\phi_v^0 = \bar{V}_2^0$) and the slope S_v^0 for the electrolytes are given in Table 1.

The ϕ_v^0 values are positive and large indicating the presence of positive solute-solvent interactions. It is also observed that ϕ_v^0 is higher in the solvent mixture containing higher percentage of formic acid for any salt under investigation. This may be explained by the two factors: (i) preferential solvation of the ions^{16,17} by the different species present in the solvent system, and (ii) interactions between the molecules of formic acid and acetonitrile. The ϕ_v^0 values follow the order at each solvent composition, Ba-salt > Ca-salt > K-salt > Li-salt > Na-salt. Smaller the size of the cation, greater is the ionic association or electrostriction and less is the ϕ_v^0 value. So the trend in ϕ_v^0 parallels the cationic size except lithium salt. The S_v^0 values are positive but the magnitude decreases with the increase in percentage of formic acid. This is attributed to the change in the dielectric constant of the medium. Generally, higher the dielectric constant of the medium lower or negative will be the S_v^0 and vice versa. S_v^0 values follow the order, Ba-salt > Ca-salt > K-salt > Na-salt > Li-salt.

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